

Status revision of two endemic *Megascolex* Templeton, 1844 subspecies from the Western Ghats of Kerala State, India (Clitellata, Megascolecidae)

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Abstract. The earthworm genus *Megascolex* Templeton, 1844, is restricted to Peninsular India and Sri Lanka. Herein this work the status of the two endemic *Megascolex* subspecies, namely, *M. konkanensis longus* Stephenson, 1915, and *M. cochinchinensis phaseolus* Stephenson, 1915, are revised based on a collection of specimens from the Parambikulam Tiger Reserve of Kerala State, India, where the type locality Parambikulam is situated. Detailed descriptions of *M. konkanensis longus* Stephenson, 1915 and *M. cochinchinensis phaseolus* Stephenson, 1915 are provided along with illustrations of the key characters. Based on the current study, both subspecies are elevated to species rank as *M. longus* and *M. phaseolus*.

Keywords. Annelida, *Megascolex cochinchinensis phaseolus*, *Megascolex konkanensis longus*, Oligochaeta, Parambikulam Tiger Reserve, taxonomy.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Megascolex* Templeton, 1844 belonging to the family Megascolecidae Rosa, 1891, is considered as one among the advanced megascolecid genera (Blakemore 2012). This earthworm genus is exclusive to two South Asian nations, India and Sri Lanka, where it is restricted to Peninsular India (primarily in the Western Ghats and Eastern Ghats) and Sri Lanka (Stephenson 1923, Gates 1941, 1945, Narayanan *et al.* 2020, 2021a, 2023a, Naik *et al.* 2024).

Hitherto 71 valid taxa are known in this genus (Narayanan *et al.* 2020, 2021a, 2023a, 2024a, Lone *et al.* 2022, Naik *et al.* 2024). Thirty-four of these species are endemic to Peninsular India while 36 taxa are restricted to Sri Lanka, with one

species, *M. insignis* Michaelsen, 1910 is found in both countries (Michaelsen 1910, Stephenson 1923, Narayanan *et al.* 2024a).

Several earthworm species described from the Indian subcontinent are known only from their respective type localities or from the original description (Narayanan *et al.* 2021a, 2023a, 2024b) and species of the genus *Megascolex* is not an exception. Although in recent years, many of these species have been collected from additional localities (Narayanan *et al.* 2014, 2023b, c, Sathrumithra *et al.* 2018, Anuja *et al.* 2023). However, several *Megascolex* species from the present day Kerala State were scientifically described a century ago (Narayanan *et al.* 2016), and since then, studies on the genus in the state have been limited. Hence, due to the lack of revisionary

works, the taxonomic status of many of these species, their level of morphological variation etc. cannot be considered as confirmed.

In 1915, Stephenson described a new variety of *Megascolex konkanensis* Fedarb, 1898 based on two specimens, naming it *M. konkanensis* var. *longus*. In the same work he described another species, *M. phaseolus*, its description was based on three specimens, two of which were posteriorly incomplete. But later he treated it as a variety of *M. cochinchinensis* Stephenson, 1915 (Stephenson 1923). In this study, we re-evaluate the taxonomic status of these two endemic *Megascolex* subspecies, based on newly collected specimens from their type locality in the Parambikulam Tiger Reserve of Kerala State, India. The characteristics of these two subspecies are very different from the respected nominate species, so our firm belief is that it should be elevated to its own species rank, rather than being kept at the subspecies level. Therefore, our comprehensive analysis based on the traditional morphological and anatomical features supports the elevation of both to species status, here designated as *M. longus* Stephenson, 1915 and *M. phaseolus* Stephenson, 1915.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection and preservation. Earthworms were collected from various locations of the Parambikulam Tiger Reserve, Palakkad district of Kerala State, in the southwestern Indian peninsula. Collections were made by digging the soil with a spade, and hand-sorting the soil for earthworms. Specimens collected were preserved in 10% formalin. All relevant morphological and anatomical observations were conducted through dorsal dissection under a Magnus MSZ series stereomicroscope. Illustrations were made with the help of a camera lucida attached to the microscope. Colour images were taken using a Nikon stereomicroscope (Model: SMZ800N). Raw images and line drawings were improved using Adobe Photoshop. Collected specimens were deposited in the earthworm laboratory of the Advanced Centre of Environmental Studies and

Sustainable development (ACCESSD), Mahatma Gandhi University, Kerala, India.

General abbreviations of the terms used. C. = Clitellum, F.P. = Female pore, G. = Genital marking, Gr. = Groove, M. = Male field, M.P. = Male pore, Pr. = Prostate gland, Pr.D. = Prostatic duct, Sp.A. = Spermathecal ampulla, Sp.D. = Spermathecal duct, Sp.Div. = Spermathecal diverticulum, Sp.P. = Spermathecal pore.

Institutional abbreviations. ACCESSD: Advanced Centre of Environmental Studies and Sustainable Development, Mahatma Gandhi University, Kottayam, Kerala, India; ZSIC: Zoological Survey of India, Kolkata, India.

TAXONOMY

Family Megascolecidae Rosa, 1891

Genus *Megascolex* Templeton, 1844

Megascolex longus Stephenson, 1915 stat. rev.

(Figures 1A–F)

Megascolex konkanensis var. *longus* Stephenson, 1915: 97.

Megascolex konkanensis var. *longus*: Stephenson 1923: 255.

Megascolex konkanensis longus: Blakemore 2007: 35; Narayanan et al. 2016: 128; 2023a: 192; 2025a: 20.

Type locality. Parambikulam, Kerala State, India (10.3986°N 76.7730°E); *Type.* ZSIC 6602 (Narayanan et al. 2023a).

Material examined. 2 clitellates (one specimen posteriorly incomplete) (ACCESSD/EW/638), 63 Vayal (10°23'55" N 76°46'13.6" E) in Parambikulam Tiger Reserve, Palakkad District, Kerala, *vayal* (open salt lick sites), 584 m a.s.l., 3 August 2016, leg. S. Prasanth Narayanan, Toms Augustine and S. Sathrumithra; 1 clitellate (posteriorly incomplete) (ACCESSD/EW/652), Vagapallom (on the way to Thoothanpara) (10°27'38.7"N, 76°43'1.1"E) in Parambikulam Tiger Reserve, Palakkad District, Kerala, 652 m a.s.l., moist

Figure 1. *Megascolex longus* Stephenson, 1915: A = Image of the clitellum and male field; B = Illustration of the clitellum and male field; C = Image of the spermathecal pore region; D = Illustration of a spermatheca, dorsal view; E = Image of spermathecae; F = Prostates, dorsal view. Line drawings are without scale.

deciduous forest, 3 August 2016, leg. S. Prasanth Narayanan, S. Sathrumithra, Toms Augustine and Vishnu Vijayan.

Description. External. Dimensions: Length 345–570, width 3–4 mm, segments 400–550. Anterior end truncated. Prostomium combined pro/epilobic, tongue open. First dorsal pore in intersegmental furrow 5/6. Setae perichaetine throughout; $aa = 2$ $ab = 2.5$ $bc = 2$ $yz = 0.7$ zz on segment 12; $aa = 3.2$ $ab = 5.3$ $bc = 2$ $yz = 1.3$ zz on segment 24 ($n = 1$); setae absent between male pores. Clitellum annular, not prominent, light buff colour (in preservation), on segments 14–17 (= 4), dorsal pore indication present, intersegmental furrows distinct, setae visible. Male genital region confined to segment 18 (Fig. 1A, B), male pore minute, at about centres of medially conjoined slightly depressed oval porophores, in *c* line, 0.13–0.14 body circumference apart. Female pore minute, single, pre-setal, ventro-median, on segment 14. Spermathecal pores very minute, at about *d* line, in intersegmental furrows 7/8/9 (Fig.

1C), 0.16 body circumference apart. Genital markings and penial setae absent.

Internal. Septum 5/6 delicate, 6/7–12/13 muscular. Oesophageal gizzard large, muscular, barrel-shaped in segment 5; intestine begins in segment 19; typhlosole absent. Last pair of hearts in segment 13. Holandric, testes and male funnels paired, free in segment 10 and 11; seminal vesicles in segment 9 and 12. Spermathecae paired in segments 8 and 9, ampulla ovoid, with an ectal club-shaped diverticulum about half as long as combined length of duct and ampulla (Fig. 1D, E). Prostate small, paired, confined to segment 18, bushy, with many lobules; ducts straight, ectal end bulged (Fig. 1F). Excretory system micromeronephric; large bushy tufts anterior to gizzards; nephridia absent on parietes segment anterior to clitellum; small four to six bushy tufts, in transverse band in clitellar segments, arranged between setal row and anterior septum; behind clitellum, numerous, small nephridia, in single transverse band in parietes, arranged at middle septum.

Figure 2. *Megascolex konkanensis* Fedarb, 1898: A = Ventral view; B = Prostate; C = Spermathecae. Figure courtesy: Anuja et al. (2024).

Variation. In the Vagapallom specimen (ACCESSD/EW/652), prostate glands are lightly antero-posteriorly placed.

Ingesta. Fine mineralized soil and sand particles.

Habitat. Moist deciduous forest and Vayal (open salt lick sites) inside the moist deciduous forest.

Ecology. Seems to be an endogeic species, as indicated by large quantity of mineralised soil and sand particles in the intestine.

Distribution. India: Kerala State: Palakkad District: Endemic to Parambikulam Tiger Reserve: 63 Vayal, Parambikulam, Vagapallom - on the way to Thoothanpara (Stephenson 1915, Narayanan *et al.* 2025a).

Remarks. Dimension of the full length worm from the present collection is the following: length 421 mm, width (mid clitellar) 3 mm, seg-

ments 481. Initially it was described as a variety of *M. konkanensis konkanensis* Fedarb, 1898 as *M. k. var. longus* Stephenson 1915. The nominate, *M. konkanensis* is a widespread endemic species to Southwestern India, with a few records from outside this domain such as Lakshadweep Islands Union Territory, Rajasthan and Tamil Nadu States (Narayanan *et al.* 2023a). There are substantial differences between the *M. k. longus* and the nominate *M. k. konkanensis*: 1) in female pores (single in *M. k. longus* vs paired in *M. k. konkanensis*), 2) shape of the male field, 3) prostate (small, bushy vs very large, mop-like), and 4) spermathecae (ovoid vs pear-shaped) (Fig. Fig. 1D, E, 2C, also see Fedarb 1898, Michaelsen 1910, Stephenson 1923, Narayanan *et al.* 2024c). A comparison of certain important characters of these species is provided in table 1. Therefore, based on the present study, the status of the *M. k. longus* is revised and it is elevated to species rank as *M. longus* Stephenson, 1915.

Table 1. Comparison of the characters of *Megascolex konkanensis* Fedarb, 1898 and *M. longus* Stephenson, 1915

Character	<i>M. konkanensis</i> Fedarb, 1898 ^{1,2,3,4}	<i>M. longus</i> Stephenson, 1915 ^{3,5,*}
Length	78–450 mm	345–570 mm
Diameter	2–3 mm	3–4 mm
Segments	216–370	400–550
Prostomium	Epilobous, small, tongue narrow	Combined pro/epilobic, tongue open
First dorsal pore	In intersegmental furrow 4/5	In intersegmental furrow 5/6
Clitellum	Annular, in segments 14–16, ½17 (= 3½)	Annular, in segments 14–17 (= 4)
Female pore	Paired	Single
Male field	Each male pore in a large, separate, oval area	Each male pore, at about centres of medially conjoined slightly depressed oval porophore
Genital marking	Absent	Absent
Gizzard	Large, in segment 5	Large barrel shaped in segment 5
Intestine origin	In segment 16	In segment 19
Spermathecae	Stalked, ampulla pear-shaped, ectal club-shaped diverticulum, about half length of the ampulla	Not stalked, ampulla ovoid, ectal club-shaped diverticulum, about half as long as combined length of duct and ampulla
Prostate	Large, mop-like, duct thick, fairly long, muscular and thinner at the end	Small, bushy, duct straight, ectal end bulged

Data from: ¹Fedarb (1898); ²Michaelsen (1910); ³Stephenson (1923); ⁴Anuja *et al.* (2023); ⁵Stephenson (1915); *Present study.

***Megascolex phaseolus* Stephenson, 1915
stat. rev.**

(Figure 3A–D)

Megascolex phaseolus Stephenson, 1915: 93.

Megascolex cochinensis var. *phaseolus*: Stephenson 1923: 238.

Megascolex cochinensis phaseolus: Blakemore 2007: 33; Narayanan et al. 2016: 127; 2023a: 188; 2025a: 20.

Type locality. Parambikulam, Kerala State, India (10.3986°N 76.7730°E); *Type*. ZSIC 6601 (Narayanan et al. 2023a).

Material examined. 3 clitellates, 1 a clitellate (ACESSD/EW/627), between Parambikulam tunnel entry and Vengolimala camp shed (10°25'10.0"N 76°48'16.1"E) in Parambikulam Tiger Reserve, Palakkad District, Kerala, 784 m a.s.l., moist deciduous forest, 1 August 2016, leg. S. Prasanth Narayanan, Toms Augustine and S. Sathrumithra; 3 clitellates (ACESSD/EW/629), Parambikulam Dam site (10°23'19.2" N 76°46'5.5" E) in Parambikulam Tiger Reserve, Palakkad District, Kerala, 519 m a.s.l., disturbed semi evergreen forest, 1 August 2016, leg. S. Prasanth Narayanan, Toms Augustine and S. Sathrumithra; 2 clitellates and 1 a clitellate (ACESSD/EW/632), Thoonakkadavu (10°26'13.2" N 76°46'9.3" E) in Parambikulam Tiger Reserve, Palakkad District, Kerala, 554 m a.s.l., *Tectona grandis* plantation, 2 August 2016, leg. S. Prasanth Narayanan; 3 clitellates (ACESSD/EW/634), below Karimalagopuram hill (10°21'48" N 76°45'9.3" E) in Parambikulam Tiger Reserve, Palakkad District, Kerala, 1153 m a.s.l., evergreen forest, 2 August 2016, leg. S. Prasanth Narayanan, Toms Augustine and S. Sathrumithra; 1 clitellate (lightly indicated) (ACESSD/EW/642), Kuriyarkutty (10°24'45.6" N 76°43'4" E) in Parambikulam Tiger Reserve, Palakkad District, Kerala, 513 m a.s.l., *Tectona grandis* plantation, 3 August 2016, leg. S. Prasanth Narayanan, S. Sathrumithra, Toms Augustine and Vishnu Vijayan; 3 a clitellates (ACESSD/EW/654), Karianchola (10° 27'37.1" N 76°49'44.5" E) in Parambikulam Tiger Reserve, Palakkad District, Kerala, 733 m a.s.l., evergreen

forest, 4 August 2016, leg. S. Prasanth Narayanan, Toms Augustine and S. Sathrumithra.

Description. *External*. Dimensions: Length 152–377, width 3–4.5 mm (mid clitellar), 236–382 segments. Prostomium small, epilobic, tongue closed. First dorsal pore in intersegmental furrow 5/6. Setae perichaetine throughout; $aa = 1.7-2$ $ab = 1.3-2.5$ $bc = 0.5-0.6$ $yz = 0.19-0.20$ zz on segment 12; $aa = 3.8-5$ $ab = 3-5$ $bc = 2-3$ $yz = 0.63-0.68$ zz on segment 24 ($n = 2$); 10–15 on segment 2, 33–46 on segment 8, 47 on segment 12, 48 on segment 20; setae absent between male pores. Clitellum annular, brownish or reddish brown colour (in preservation), on segments 14–17 (= 4), dorsal pores occluded, intersegmental furrows indistinct, setae visible. Male pores in oblique slits at median and posterior interrupted ends of an elliptical ridge surrounding a kidney-shaped median tumescence on segment 18 (Fig. 3A, B), 0.04 body circumference apart, fine seminal grooves extend from male pores anteriorly onto median kidney-shaped tumescence. Female pore minute, single, pre-setal, ventro-median, on segment 14. Spermathecal pores small, at ab lines, in intersegmental furrows 7/8/9 (Fig. 3C, D), 0.05 body circumference apart. Genital markings usually present, single, median pre-setal on segment 19, penial setae absent.

Internal. Septum 5/6 delicate, septa 6/7–12/13 muscular. Oesophageal gizzard large, muscular, barrel-shaped, in segment 5; oesophagus without calciferous glands; intestine begins in segment 19; typhlosole absent. Last pair of hearts in segment 13. Holandric, testes and male funnels paired, free in segment 10 and 11; seminal vesicles in segment 9 and 12. Spermathecae paired in segments 8 and 9 (Fig. 4A), ampulla about elongately club-shaped, each with a club-shaped ectal diverticulum, shorter than combined length of duct and ampulla, almost equal or shorter than the duct; duct longer than ampulla (Fig. 4B). Prostate paired, confined to segment 18, somewhat flattened, lobed and compacted together; duct straight, stout, slimmer towards ental end (Fig. 4C). Excretory system micromeronephric; large large bushy tufts anterior to gizzards in segment 3

Figure 3. *Megascolex phaseolus* Stephenson, 1915: A = Image of the clitellum and male field, ventral view; B = Illustration of the clitellum and male field, ventral view; C = Image of the spermathecal pore region, ventral view; D = Illustration of the spermathecal pore region, ventral view. Line drawings are without scale.

and 4, about middle line; nephridia absent on parietes segment anterior to clitellum; small bushy tufts, in clitellar segments; behind clitellum, numerous, small nephridia, in transverse band in parietes, arranged behind anterior septum.

Ingesta. Colloids of fine soil and small particles of bark like organic materials.

Habitat. A variety of forest types such as disturbed semi evergreen, evergreen and moist

deciduous forests and teak *Tectona grandis* plantation.

Ecology. Seems to be an endo-aneceic species, as indicated by fine soil and small pieces of bark like organic materials in the intestine.

Distribution. India: Kerala State: Palakkad District: Endemic to Parambikulam Tiger Reserve: below Karimalagopuram hill, between Parambikulam tunnel entry and Vengolimala camp shed, Karianchola, Kuriyarkutty, Parambikulam,

Parambikulam Dam site, Thoonakkadavu (Stephenson 1915, Narayanan *et al.* 2025a) (Fig. 5).

Remarks. Stephenson (1915) in his original description of the species, stated that the gizzard as ‘ovoid’, although made no mention of it in his (1923) ‘Fauna of British India – Oligochaeta’. But the present study confirmed that the gizzard is barrel-shaped in this species. *M. phaseolus* was initially described at species rank by Stephenson (1915), but later he treated it as a variety of *M. cochinensis cochinensis* Stephenson, 1915 (Stephenson 1923) (Fig. 6). *M. cochinensis* is an endemic species, which is mainly found in Kerala State with one record from the Tamil Nadu State

(Kathireswari *et al.* 2008, Narayanan *et al.* 2023a). Later, Blakemore (2007) treated *M. phaseolus* as a subspecies of *M. cochinensis*. However, both *M. cochinensis phaseolus* and *M. cochinensis cochinensis* displays drastic differences in the organization of male field (Fig. 3A, B vs Fig. 6A; also see figures in Stephenson 1915, 1923), genital marking (usually present vs absent), and spermathecae (ampulla club-shaped vs ovoid).

Comparison of certain key characters of these two species is provided in table 2. Hence, based on the present study, *M. cochinensis phaseolus* is elevated to species rank as *M. phaseolus* Stephenson, 1915.

Figure 4. *Megascolex phaseolus* Stephenson, 1915: A = Image of the spermathecae, dorsal view; B = Illustration of a spermatheca; C = Image of the prostate, right side, dorsal view. Line drawing is without scale.

Table 2. Detailed comparison of *Megascolex cochinensis* Stephenson, 1915 and *M. phaseolus* Stephenson, 1915

Character	<i>M. cochinensis</i> Stephenson, 1915 ^{1,2,3}	<i>M. phaseolus</i> Stephenson, 1915 ^{1,2,*}
Length	46–220 mm	152–377 mm
Diameter	2–4 mm	3–4.5 mm
Segments	56–224	236–382
Prostomium	Epilobous, tongue cut off behind	Proepilobous or epilobous
First dorsal pore	In intersegmental furrow 5/6	In intersegmental furrow 5/6
Clitellum	Annular, in segments 14– $\frac{2}{3}$ 17, (= 3 $\frac{2}{3}$)	Annular, in segments 14–17 (= 4)
Female pore	Single	Single
Male field	Male pores as oblique wavy slits, the posterior ends of which approach each other on a white oval elevation, also oblique which almost touches in the middle line, the area surrounding the papillae depressed, and the whole surrounded by an oval wall	Male pores in oblique slits at median and posterior interrupted ends of an elliptical ridge surrounding a kidney-shaped median tumescence on segment 18, fine seminal grooves extend from male pores anteriorly onto median kidney-shaped tumescence
Genital marking	Absent	Present
Gizzard	Large barrel shaped in segment 5	Large barrel shaped in segment 5
Intestine origin	In segment 19	In segment 19
Last heart	In segment 13	In segment 13
Spermathecae	Ampulla ovoid, ectal club-shaped diverticulum, reaching about to middle of ampulla	Ampulla elongately club-shaped, ectal club-shaped diverticulum, almost equal or shorter than the duct
Prostate	Confined to segment 18, mass of small solid, roundish looking mass, duct muscular, wider at ental end	Confined to segment 18, somewhat flattened, lobed and compacted together, duct straight, stout, slimmer towards ental end

Data from: ¹Stephenson (1915); ²Stephenson (1923); ³Anuja *et al.* (2023); *Present study.

DISCUSSION

Within the Western Ghats mountain stretch, various earthworm groups show a distinct distributional pattern; acanthodrilid worms dominates the northern part of the Western Ghats up to southern Karnataka, whereas, southern Western Ghats is dominated by the megascolecid and moniligastrid species (Narayanan *et al.* 2020).

Recently, several new moniligastrid species have been described or newly reported from the Western Ghats, especially from the southern portion (Narayanan *et al.* 2017, 2021b, 2022, 2024d, e, 2025b). However, after independence, Jamieson (1977) and Lone (2022) has described a number of new species of the family Megascole-

cidae, while Sathrumithra *et al.* (2018), Narayanan *et al.* (2019a, b, 2023b, c, 2024c, 2025c), Lone (2022) and Anuja *et al.* (2023, 2024), rediscovered or mentioned about several megascolecid species from the Southern Western Ghats.

Most of the *Megascolex* species are restricted to the southern Western Ghats (Narayanan *et al.* 2016, 2023a) and as stated earlier, due to the lack of revisionary work, the taxonomic status and level of morphological variation etc. of many of these species are not well understood. Hence, the present work on the status revision of two *Megascolex* subspecies is a step in the right direction. By providing the detailed descriptions, illustrations of the key characters of *M. konkanensis longus* Stephenson, 1915 and *M. cochinensis*

Figure 5. Current known distribution of *Megascolex longus* Stephenson, 1915 and *M. phaseolus* Stephenson, 1915

Figure 6. *Megascolex cochinensis* Stephenson, 1915. A = Ventral view; B = Prostate; C = Spermathecae. Figure courtesy: Anuja *et al.* (2024).

phaseolus Stephenson, 1915 and comparison with the nominate subspecies, these two subspecies are elevated to species rank as *M. longus* and *M. phaseolus*.

Until recently both, *M. longus* and *M. phaseolus* were known only from the type locality Parambikulam (Narayanan *et al.* 2023a, 2025a). Apart from the type locality, *M. longus* is collected from two additional locations, whereas *M. phaseolus* were collected from additional six locations within the Parambikulam Tiger Reserve. This indicates a wider distribution of these species in the Parambikulam landscape.

Previously, apart from the taxonomy nothing much was known about the ecology, distribution of these two species. Present study has put further lights into the ecology and biological aspects of these two enigmatic earthworm species. We hope that, present work will help to design the species specific conservation action plan in the future.

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